

Role of Rhodamine B in photovoltage generation using anionic surfactant in liquid phase photoelectrochemical cell for solar energy conversion and storage

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Abstract : The conversion of solar energy on the basis of photogalvanic effect in liquid phase photogalvanic solar cell is studied experimentally. The photogalvanic effect has been studied in system containing Rhodamine B as a photosensitizer and DTPA as a reducing agent in presence of sodium lauryl sulphate. The photopotential and photocurrent generated by this system were 843.0 mV and 185.0 μ A, respectively. The experimental conversion efficiency, fill factor, storage capacity of this cell have also been determined. The effect of different parameters on electrical output of the cell like effect of dye, reductant and surfactant concentration, pH, light intensity, temperature, diffusion length and electrode area were investigated. The absorption properties of newly used dye (Rhodamine B) were analyzed. This photogalvanic cell can be used for 85.0 min in dark. A mechanism of cell photochemical reaction has also been proposed.

Keywords : Rhodamine B, solar energy, cell, surfactant, photovoltage.

Introduction

The use of photogalvanic cell for conversion and storage of solar energy is highly appreciated. Some interesting photogalvanic cell systems were reported by many workers time to time¹. Sensitization of an iron-thionine photogalvanic cell to the blue – an improved match to the insolation spectrum has been reported². Recently, we and other workers have reported effective photogalvanic response of dyes in micellar media³. The present work will be an effort to study the electroactive species and to observe various electrical parameters of photogalvanic cell in NaLS-Rhodamine B-DTPA system.

Results and discussion

In the spectral studies of Rhodamine B, at dye concentration $1.68 \times 10^{-5} M$ shows maximum absorption in the visible region at 550 nm. Absorption properties of dye + surfactant solution were also observed and the spectrum is shown in Fig. 1. Maximum absorption peak is recorded at dye-surfactant combination of concentration $1.68 \times 10^{-5} M + 1.04 \times 10^{-3} M$.

The results showing effect of variation of pH on electrical output of the cell are graphically represented in Fig. 2. Photogalvanic cell containing NaLS-Rhodamine

B-DTPA system was found to be quite sensitive to the pH of the solution. The electrical output of photogalvanic cell was affected by the variation in pH of the system. There is an increase in the photopotential and photocurrent of this system with increase in pH in the alkaline range. At pH 13.20 a maxima was obtained and thereafter a decrease has been observed.

The anionic surfactant sodium lauryl sulphate is used as micelle in this system. With increasing surfactant concentration the photopotential and photocurrent of the cell also increases, attaining a maximum and decreases on further increase in surfactant concentration. The most important properties of micellar systems are the ability to solubilize a variety of molecules and substantial catalytic effect on many chemical reactions⁴. Photoinduced electron transfer processes in micellar systems are potentially important for efficient energy conversion and storage because surfactant micelles help to achieve the separation of photoproducts by hydrophilic-hydrophobic interaction of the products with the micellar interface⁵.

With increase in the concentration of the reductant (DTPA), the photopotential and photocurrent increases to maximum and then decreases. The fall in power output with decrease in concentration of reductant is due to less availability of molecules for electron donation to the cat-

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of dye and dye + surfactant.

ionic form of dye. The photogalvanic effect was observed by variation of the concentration of Rhodamine B as photosensitizer. On the basis of results obtained, it is observed that there is an increase in photopotential (V_{oc}) and photocurrent (i_{sc}) values on increasing the concentration of the dye. On the lower side of the concentration range of dye, there are a limited number of dye molecules to absorb the major portion of the light in the path and, therefore low electrical output is (photopotential and photocurrent) obtained.

Effect of diffusion length on the electrical output (i_{max}) and initial rate of generation of current of the photogalvanic cell were observed by using H-cell of different dimensions. The diffusion length (distance between the electrodes) greatly affects this system. i_{max} was found to increase with diffusion length but i_{eq} shows a negligible

effect in the photocurrent in first few minutes of illumination and then there was a gradual decrease to a stable value of photocurrent. The Dye^- and Dye are electro active species in illuminated and dark chambers respectively. In illuminated chamber Dye^- strike at Pt electrode and donate electron to electrode which moves through external circuit to reach calomel electrode (in dark chamber), electro active species dye strike at calomel electrode and accept electron from it then through diffusion Dye^- reach to Pt and Dye diffuse to dark chamber. Thus the electrical output depends on diffusion and conductivity of the Dye. The conductivity of electroactive species depends on its population between electrodes. As the diffusion length is increased the volume of dye solution and intern population of dye molecules (Dye) increased leading higher i_{max} . The electro active nature of Dye/Dye^- is

Fig. 2. Variation of photopotential, photocurrent and power with pH.

proved by the fact that i_{max} increases with diffusion length. Therefore, it may be concluded that the main electro active species are the leuco or semi form of Dye^- and the Dye in the illuminated and the dark chamber respectively. The reductant and its oxidation product act only as electron carries in the path.

The open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and short circuit current (i_{sc}) of the photogalvanic cell are measured under the continuous illumination of light, with the help of a digital pH meter (keeping the circuit open) and a microammeter (keeping the circuit closed), respectively. The external parameters (photopotential and photocurrent) of photogalvanic cell in between these two extreme values (V_{pp} and i_{pp}) were recorded with the help of a carbon pot (log 470 K) connected in the circuit of micro

ammeter, through which an external load applied on it. $i-V$ curves deviated from standard regular rectangular shape. $i-V$ curve is given in Fig. 3 (found in standard condition of 0 °C and 1000 W/m² insolation and in typical condition 25 °C and 800 W/m² insolation for the solar cells). The maximum power point (pp) is obtained by plotting the current-voltage ($i-V$) curve and choosing the value of V_{max} and i_{max} , which gave the largest area under the $i-V$ curve. The easy way is to plot the product of photopotential and current as a function of photopotential (mV), which gives a maximum value for certain value of photopotential and photocurrent (Fig. 3). These values are put into the expression (1) and (2) for fill factor and solar energy conversion efficiency of the cell consisting of Rhodamine B in anionic micelle solution. The power

NaLS - Rhodamine B - DTPA System

Fig. 3. Current-voltage (*i-V*) curve of the cell.

point (a point on the curve where the product of potential and current is maximum) on this *i-V* curve was determined and their fill factor was also calculated which represents the efficiency of the cell.

The value of fill factor and energy conversion efficiency were calculated by using eqs. (1) and (2).

$$\text{Fill factor (ff)} = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{V_{oc} \times i_{sc}} \quad (1)$$

Energy conversion efficiency (η)

$$\frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{A \times 10^{-4} \text{ mW/cm}^2} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

where, V_{pp} , i_{pp} , V_{oc} , i_{sc} are the potential at power point, current at power point, open circuit photovoltage and short circuit current, respectively and A is electrode area. Values of conversion efficiency, fill factor were obtained as 0.74% and 0.4955 in NaLS-Rhodamine B-DTPA system.

The storage capacity (Performance) of the photogalvanic cell system containing NaLS-Rhodamine B-DTPA

was determined by applying the desired external load with keeping the cell at the power point stage in dark and noted down the time required in fall of power output to its half value. Storage capacity of the photogalvanic cell system is denoted by $t_{1/2}$, which is the measure of performance of the cell. It was observed that cell can be used in the dark for 85.0 min.

The chemically reactive species is the triplet state of dye specially, in the presence of electron donating substances the dye is excited by light and rapidly changed into reduced (colorless) form. The dye acts as a reducing agent and will be donating electrons to other substances and being returned to its oxidized state. On the basis of these observations a mechanism is suggested for the generation of electrical output in photogalvanic cell as follows :

Illuminated chamber :

At platinum electrode :

Dark chamber :

At SCE :

where, Dye, Dye⁻, R and R⁺ represents the dye (RB), reduced form of dye, reductant and oxidized form of reductant, respectively.

Energy storage mechanism : This cell undergoes cyclical charging and discharging process. The charging of cell occurs only in presence of illuminating source. The discharging of cell takes place only when we apply the external circuit for electron transfer. As long as there is no external circuit, the cell will keep light energy stored. For how long cell will store light energy depends on stability of excited state of dye and population of excited dye molecules. The storage capacity of the cell will be higher if excited dye molecules are more stable due to its bulkiness or amount of delocalization of excited electrons on it or if for any reason say, due to recombination of D⁻

and R⁺ as a result of diffusion, the concentration of dye is reduced, the storage capacity of cell is also reduced. So, we the authors are planning to carryout further research with a view to stop this recombination of D⁻ and R⁺. In this direction Ghosh and Bhattacharya⁶ used H-shaped cell in which illuminated and dark chambers were separated by Pyrex sintered glass membrane to prevent recombination of D⁻ and R⁺.

Experimental

Rhodamine B obtained from Sisco Chem., anionic surfactant (NaLS) is Sisco Chem.'s product and (DTPA) is Loba chemise's product. Conductivity water was used throughout. Concentration of Rhodamine B, NaLS and DTPA solutions were ($1.68 \times 10^{-5} M$), ($1.04 \times 10^{-3} M$) and ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$), respectively. The pH of the solution was maintained at 13.20 by mixing 1 N sodium hydroxide solution (NaOH was Ranbaxy's product) against standardized with 1 N oxalic acid solution.

Structure of compounds used :

Rhodamine B ($C_{28}H_{31}N_2O_3Cl$)

DTPA (Diethylene triamine pentaacetic acid) ($C_{14}H_{23}N_3O_{10}$)

NaLS (Sodium lauryl sulphate) ($NaC_{12}H_{25}SO_4$)

Fig. 4. Set-up of photogalvanic cell.

Absorption spectra were recorded using Hergestell inder DDR UV-Visible spectrophotometer. All spectral measurements were duplicated in a constant temperature water bath maintained within ± 0.1 °C and mean values were processed for data analysis. Photogalvanic effect was measured by a H-shaped glass cell. Platinum foil electrode (1.0 cm^2) is placed at the centre of one compartment and saturated calomel electrode was immersed in another compartment. The cell was filled with known amount of aqueous solution of dye, reductant, surfactant and NaOH. The whole system was first placed in the dark. When it attains stable potential, this dark potential was noted. Now the platinum electrode compartment was exposed to tungsten lamp. A water filter was placed between cell and light source to cut off thermal radiations. Photovoltage and photocurrent were measured with a digital pH meter (Systronics model 335) and a micro ammeter (OSAW-1632/A). Current-voltage (i - V) characteristics of the cell were studied using an external load (log 470 K) in circuit. A set-up of photogalvanic cell is given in Fig. 4.

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References

1. M. Kaneko and A. Yamada, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1977, **81**, 1213; A. S. N. Murthy and K. S. Reddy, *Int. J. Energy Res.*, 1979, **3**, 205; A. S. N. Murthy, H. C. Dak and K. S. Reddy, *Int. J. Energy Res.*, 1980, **4**, 339; A. S. N. Murthy and K. S. Reddy, *Solar Energy*, 1983, **30**, 39; *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1984, **12**, 2023; K. K. Rohatgi-Mukherjee, M. Roy and B. B. Bhowmik, *Solar Energy*, 1983, **31**, 417; S. C. Ameta, P. K. Jain, A. K. Janoo and R. Ameta, *The Energy Journal*, 1985, **58**, 8; S. C. Ameta, R. Ameta, D. Sharma and T. D. Dubey, *Hung. J. Ind. Chem.*, 1987, **15**, 377; S. C. Ameta, T. D. Dubey, D. Sharma and R. Ameta, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1988, **269**, 850; S. C. Ameta, S. Khamesra, N. K. Jain and K. M. Gangotri, *Pol. J. Chem.*, 1991, **65**, 1415; M. A. Fox and Kabir-ud-din, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1979, **83**, 1800; M. Sharon, S. G. Sharan, B. M. Prasad, A. P. Bholgir and R. R. Pradhananga, "SUN, Mankind's Future Source of Energy", 'Proceedings of the International Solar Energy Society Congress', New Delhi, India, 1978; M. Sharon and A. Sinha, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, 1982, **7**, 557.
2. P. D. Wildes, D. R. Hobart, N. N. Lichtin, D. E. Hall and J. A. Eckert, *Solar Energy*, 1977, **19**, 567.
3. B. B. Bhowmik and P. Ganguly, *Spectrochimica Acta, Part A : Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 2005, **61**, 1997; 2005, **62**, 808; K. R. Genwa and Mahaveer, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2007, **46**, 91; K. R. Genwa and A. Sonel, *J.*

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- Indian Council Chem.*, 2007, 24, 78.
4. J. H. Fendler and E. J. Fendler, "Catalysis in Micellar and Macromolecular Systems", Academic Press, New York, 1975; D. Attwood and A. T. Florence, "Surfactant Systems", Chapman and Hall, New York, 1983.
 5. Y. Moroi, P. P. Infelte and M. Gratzel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 101, 573; K. K. Rohatgi-Mukherjee, R. Choudhary and B. B. Bhowmik, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1985, 106, 45.
 6. J. K. Ghosh and S. C. Bhattacharya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, 79, 225.

